

Stress-Strain State of Composite Stay Rope for Suspending Permanent Structures and their Components

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Abstract. The purpose of research is to determine the influence character of the way the composite rope is connected to the permanent structure elements on its stress-strain state and to develop a determination method for such a state. Research methodology involves constructing the models of interaction between rigid fibers in a rope of composite design, using the methods of mechanics of layered composite materials, with complex consideration of its design and mechanical properties, and the condition of connecting rope ends to the permanent structure. The model is solved analytically using Fourier series on a discrete axis of layer numbers of a finite length while defining the distribution patterns of internal forces and displacements in rope layers. The algorithm for determining a stress-strain state of a rope with rigid fibers while considering a rope connection scheme to the permanent structure is established. The scientific novelty of research is in determination of the character and influence mechanism of a connection scheme of a composite rope with rigid fibers to the permanent structure on its stress-strain state. Practical value of the research is in that the obtained results make it possible to consider the influence character of the rope connection scheme to the permanent structure on a rope stress state and this allows justified determination of its safe operation conditions.

Introduction

In the field of construction, ropes are widely used as elements of design in permanent structures. Such permanent structures are suspension bridges, in which the spans are supported by ropes. Ropeways are structures, by which transporting devices move people and cargo along the ropes. Ropes are also used as guy-lines to support tall towers.

Such ropes are practically loaded only with tensile forces and are immovably connected to elements of structures. To ensure sufficient strength, the ropes are manufactured from metal cables. They operate for a significant time in an open-air environment as well as interaction of rope elements (like wires or cores) inside the rope.

Wires of ropes rust in open-air environment. Such a process is also accelerated by friction of wires, from which the rope is made. Making mutual friction of wires and their interaction with open-air environment impossible allows increasing rope reliability when used in the permanent structures. Technical implementation of the mentioned approach is possible by developing a rope as a composite structure, which is a system of parallel fibers connected through an elastic material, e.g. polyurethane or rubber. An analog of such a rope is a rubber-cable rope with cables (fibers) placed in several planes. Rubber-cable ropes have been operating for a significant time in the mining industry, in elevators, hoists, and other machines. The operation experience has proved their benefits.